

FRACTURE OF TOUGHENED EPOXIES AND THEIR FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In glass fiber-epoxy filament winding, the epoxy is often quite brittle. The concept of toughening with CTBN-rubber is therefore investigated. The viscosity, modulus, yield stress and G_{IC} of the epoxy matrix are measured as a function of CTBN-content. The interlaminar G_{IC} and the flexural strength of unidirectional glass fiber-epoxy composites are also measured as a function of CTBN-content. A significant increase in composite G_{IC} is observed. The flexural strength decreases and the viscosity of the matrix increases. The reasons for the observed results are discussed. It is suggested that rubber toughened epoxies are considered for filament wound structures where matrix cracking or delamination are of concern.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber composites are becoming increasingly accepted as engineering materials in highly stressed applications. One obstacle, however, is the slow processing of composites with high volume fractions of continuous fibers. A fast processing method in use today is wet filament winding. Unfortunately, many filament winding matrices are quite brittle. It seems likely that tougher matrices would significantly improve the performance of filament wound composite structures.

Several routes can be used to toughen a given thermoset with desirable processing characteristics. One is to use flexibilizers¹. This approach does, however, often cause a reduction in the glass transition temperature (T_g) as well as increased moisture absorption and decreased modulus. It has been shown that rubber modification of epoxies can provide increased fracture energy (G_{IC}) with only a minor decrease in T_g and modulus². The toughening of an epoxy for filament winding has been reported³ as well as increased burst strength of pressure vessels fabricated using rubber toughened epoxy⁴. In the present study, the objective is to investigate if CTBN-rubber (CTBN) can be used to modify a commercial epoxy system so as to improve its G_{IC} .

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

The epoxy component was based on diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) and is commercially available as Ciba-Geigy LY 556. In addition a methyltetra hydrophthalic anhydride (MHPA) curing agent, HY 917, and a methyl imidazole (MI) accelerator, DY 070, from the same company was used. The rubber used was liquid carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN), denoted Hycar 1300x8 by B.F. Goodrich Chemical Co. The chemical structures of the materials are shown in Fig.1. The formulation for

the neat epoxy resin was DGEBA 100, MHPA 90 and MI 0.5 parts per hundred by weight. CTBN-rubber was added at 10, 15 and 20 parts per hundred of epoxy by weight (phr). The reinforcement used for composite lamination was unidirectional E-glass fabric, denoted 9699 from Ahlström, Norrköping, Sweden.

Fig.1. Chemical structures of the components in the epoxy system.

2. Casting and lamination

For polymer casting, all components were mixed by hand-stirring and heated to 75°C where they were kept for 2 hours while stirring at intervals. For all compositions, vacuum was applied to the mixture for a few minutes before casting. The polymer mixture was carefully poured into a metal mold of 75°C coated with a release agent. The polymer was then cured at 110°C for 2 hours and postcured at 140°C for 6 hours. Rods for compression testing were cast in glass tubes following the same curing procedure. The glass fiber composites were fabricated using wet lay-up and hot pressing. The wet laminate was first kept at 75°C for 2 hours in the hot press. Spacers were used to control the thickness of the laminate. The laminate was then cured at 110°C for 2 hours and postcured at 140°C for 6 hours. The fiber volume fraction of the cured laminates was approximately 0.5.

3. Specimen fabrication and testing

The polymer plates and rods were removed from their molds, and machined to the required dimensions. The tensile specimens were milled to the dimensions suggested by ASTM D638M-81. Double torsion (DT) specimens for the fracture tests were cut from 5 mm thick molded plates into rectangular 98 mm long and 78 mm wide specimens with 0.5 mm deep center grooves on both faces. A notch was cut at one end of the specimen and the crack tip was sharpened by a razor blade. The tensile properties were determined according to ASTM D638M-81. The specimens were 3 mm thick and the tests were conducted at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. DT-specimens were tested at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min⁵. G_{IC} was calculated by the area method⁶.

The yield stress was determined from uniaxial compression tests according to ASTM D695-80. Compression specimens were 25 mm long and 12.5 mm in diameter. The specimens were tested in a compression tool having surfaces lubricated with molybdenum disulfide grease, at a crosshead speed of 1.3 mm/min. The true yield stress was calculated⁷ with the yield stress defined as the offset stress at 2% strain.

In order to determine composite interlaminar G_{IC} , laminate plates of 5 mm thickness were cut into 300 by 25 mm double cantilever beam specimens⁶ (DCB) with the fiber direction parallel to the longest side of the specimen. The specimens had a 0.025 mm thick fluoropolymer crack starter at the midplane of one end. Two aluminium tabs for pin loading were adhesively bonded to the specimen end with the crack starter. The DCB tests were performed at room temperature in an MTS test machine at a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min. G_{IC} was determined at crack initiation for the first increment of crack growth, using the compliance calibration technique⁶.

Flexural properties of the composites were determined at room temperature according to ASTM D790M-84. The viscosity of the polymer mixture was measured by standard Brookfield viscometry at 40°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One problem with the addition of CTBN may be increased viscosity. We therefore measured viscosity as a function of rubber-content. The results are shown in Fig.2. The maximum acceptable viscosity from a processing point of view is also included⁸. At 10 phr of CTBN the viscosity is more than twice the viscosity of the unmodified epoxy. If the temperature of the matrix bath is increased, the viscosity will be reduced. Of course, the pot-life of the epoxy will then also be reduced. Another way to reduce the viscosity is to add a reactive diluent¹.

Fig.2. Viscosity as a function of CTBN-content for an epoxy system.

In Table 1 the mechanical properties of CTBN-epoxy are presented.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of CTBN-epoxy

CTBN, phr	E, MPa	σ_y , MPa	G_{IC} , KJ/m ²
0	3080	104.9	0.11
10	2597	84.9	0.64
15	2229	68.6	1.37
20	1934	53.4	1.41

The fracture energy, G_{IC} , was also measured for the epoxy polymer as a function of CTBN-content. The results are shown in Fig.3. There is a significant increase in G_{IC} with CTBN-content.

Fig.3. Fracture energy, G_{IC} , as a function of CTBN-content for an epoxy polymer and a glass fiber-epoxy composite.

The increased G_{IC} of the polymer is related to the decreased yield stress, as discussed in detail by other workers⁵. This increases the volume of plastically deformed material at the crack-tip². The decreased modulus is a disadvantage but can be compensated by the addition of glass-beads^{5,7,9,10}. However, this approach was not successful with the present composite since the matrix viscosity was too high for successful laminate fabrication.

In Fig.3 it is also apparent that the increase in G_{IC} with CTBN-content levels out at 20 phr CTBN. Scanning electron microscopy-studies (SEM) revealed that the CTBN particle size decreased with increasing CTBN-content¹¹. At 20 phr the particle diameter was smaller than 1 μm . Small particles are likely to be less efficient in promoting shear yielding in the matrix.

We observed a lower G_{IC} at 15 phr CTBN than Maxwell et al⁵, 1.4 versus 2.2 KJ/m^2 . One reason is that our unmodified epoxy is less "toughenable", since it has a lower G_{IC} to start with, 0.1 versus 0.2 KJ/m^2 . Another reason is that in our epoxy system the CTBN may be incompletely phase separated. This is supported by the fact that the epoxy and CTBN damping peaks at their respective T_g , as measured by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), were shifted towards each other with increasing CTBN-content¹¹. This would also explain the larger reduction in modulus observed here as compared with other reports².

In Fig.3, also the interlaminar G_{IC} of the composite is shown as a function of CTBN-content. Even for low CTBN-contents, the improvement in G_{IC} is significant as compared with the unmodified system. A satisfactory transfer of matrix G_{IC} to composite interlaminar G_{IC} is observed. Hunston compared matrix G_{IC} with composite G_{IC} for several materials¹². At low matrix G_{IC} 's, he found the composite G_{IC} to be higher due to energy contributions from interactions between the crack and the fibers. At higher matrix G_{IC} , the composite G_{IC} is lower since the plastic zone size at the crack tip is significantly limited by the presence of the fibers. The present data seem to agree with this.

Table 2. Flexural strength of glass fiber-epoxy

CTBN, phr	σ_f , MPa
0	1198
10	1116
15	1035

The flexural strength of a composite can often be used as a rough measure of the compressive strength, especially if a compressive failure is observed. As can be seen in Table 2, the flexural strength decreases with CTBN-content. This may be expected from the decrease in matrix modulus with CTBN-content presented in Table 1. The theory of Rosen predicts a decrease in compressive strength with decreased matrix modulus¹³.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the addition of CTBN-rubber is a way to improve the G_{IC} of composites based on an anhydride cured epoxy for filament winding. Negative effects of the addition of CTBN-rubber include increased viscosity and decreased composite flexural strength. For composite applications where matrix cracking or delamination are of concern, e.g. pipes subjected to internal pressure¹⁴, it is expected that rubber toughening of the matrix will improve structural performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial support from the National Swedish Board for Technical Development is gratefully acknowledged.

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